

Digital Transformation in Agriculture: Applications to Improve Farmers' Welfare in Central Borneo

Goal: Low fidelity prototype (wireframe) of an agricultural app which contextually suits the farmers' needs in Central Borneo

Co-design aims: Identify effective inclusive digital solutions to support farmers

Participants: 10 farmers from each BPP

Activity	Methods/Details	Duration	Notes (Prompts and Resources)
Introduction	<p>Facilitators introduce themselves as well as present the aim and goal of the workshop.</p> <p>Participants introducing themselves, talking about their roles in the community</p>	10 minutes	<p>On-boarding participants on the workshop:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research objective • What is co-design • Goal
Discussion	<p>Facilitators lead discussion with the participants related to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the use of digital technology in agriculture • Agriculture information dissemination and current practice 	50 minutes	Facilitators ask questions to activate the discussion
Co-design	<p>Gallery walk:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitators show posters on how existing technology support agriculture activities • Facilitators guide the participants to express the benefits and challenges on using technology in supporting their agriculture activities • Do they think that apps will be better than their current measure on disseminating information (e.g. whatsapp group, social media)? Why? In what way? • Discuss: format, content, process/flow, preferences 	50 minutes (including break)	<p>Show example of app, facebook group and whatsapp</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poster of existing agriculture apps in Indonesia including the features • Poster of the use of social media as source of agriculture information • Poster of existing means to disseminate agriculture information (e.g., market price board in fresh market)
	Facilitators show the blank handphone posters assist participants to design their preferred agriculture app		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants write down their preferences over an agriculture apps on sticky notes and post them on the poster

Reflection and Closing	Facilitators present a brief summary of the Discussion section	10 minutes	
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